

HISTORICAL BACKGROUND AND SOCIOECONOMIC SIGNIFICANCE OF MODERN GHANAIAN FESTIVALS: THE CASE OF KWAHU EASTER

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ABSTRACT: Festivals represent significant sociocultural and economic events in many societies. In Ghana, traditional festivals have evolved to take on more modern dimensions. The Kwahu Easter festival in Ghana's Eastern Region exemplifies these dynamics. Once a religious event, it has become a major tourist attraction driven by secular entertainment activities. This study explored the festival's history, identified its socioeconomic significance, and examined associated tensions using mixed methods. Qualitative interviews and archival research traced the festival's origins to missionary and colonial-era influences that saw Easter gain prominence over traditional Kwahu practices. Surveys and interviews found the festival holds vital socioeconomic importance for local employment, income, infrastructure, social bonds, cultural identity, and more. However, commercialisation risks eroding the festival's religious and cultural roots. Reconciling competing stakeholder interests around economic benefits versus heritage preservation remains an ongoing challenge in sustainably managing the festival. The study recommends policies to foster more geographically equitable economic gains and balance cultural continuity with modern aspirations through multi-stakeholder coordination. Findings provide insights into navigating festival tourism development with identity and sustainability in Ghana's heritage tourism sector.

Keywords: Festival, Easter, socio-economics Significance, Kwahu

I. INTRODUCTION

The Kwahu Easter festival has become Ghana's significant cultural and tourism event. Every year, thousands of visitors from across the country and worldwide flock to the Kwahu area to participate in the celebrations. However, the festival has undergone significant changes in recent years. Once mainly a religious event to commemorate the death and resurrection of Jesus Christ, it has now taken on more secular dimensions with the addition of street parties, musical performances, paragliding competitions and other activities (Gyasi et al., 2022). The festival's growing popularity is evident in the explosion of economic opportunities it brings to the Kwahu towns. Several factors account for the increasing prominence of the Kwahu Easter festival on the national calendar. Firstly, the adoption of Easter as the paramount festival of the Kwahu people in place of traditional celebrations can be traced back to the arrival of European missionaries and Christianity in the early 20th century (Zadok, 2023). Secondly, the festival provides a platform for reunions among the widespread Kwahu diaspora to reconnect with their hometowns periodically (Gyasi et al., 2022). The festival's entertainment program has also expanded vastly in line with the growth of Ghana's show business industry. Corporate sponsorships from media houses and beverage companies enable the staging of concerts featuring top music stars to coincide with Easter festivities in Kwahu (Awal, 2022). Moreover, aggressive promotion by the local authorities and the Ghana Tourism Authority (Ackwerh, 2022) has boosted the festival's public relations since the early 2000s. The GTA has driven initiatives introducing tourist attractions like the paragliding festival and upgrading infrastructure to elevate the Kwahu Easter celebrations into world-class events to boost international arrivals and tourism earnings.

However, tensions exist between pursuing tourism-led growth through the Easter festival and preserving the local Kwahu heritage and identity. Some traditional elders have voiced misgivings about the festival's increasing commercialisation and Western cultural influences on the youth (Gyasi et al., 2022). Hence, managing the festival's impacts on sociocultural traditions remains an ongoing challenge. The Kwahu Easter festival serves as a lens for examining the complex dynamics between culture, tourism and development in Ghana. While the festival originated as a religious event, the influx of visitors over Easter weekends boosts local economies. At the same time, tensions emerge as the demands of the tourism industry and outside cultural influences interact with community traditions. Several studies have assessed the economic impacts of festivals, especially in the context of developing countries (Gyasi et al., 2022). Others have analysed interactions between hosts and guests at festivals from a social exchange theory perspective (Ahmad et al., 2023). However, few investigations have explicitly focused on the shifts at the Kwahu Easter festival regarding identity, heritage preservation and stakeholders' attitudes like traditional authorities.

II. RESEARCH QUESTIONS

1. What is the history behind the celebration of the Kwahu Easter festival?
2. How does the Kwahu Easter Festival contribute to the growth of socioeconomic Significance?

III. LITERATURE REVIEW

This section reviews related literature on the historical background of Kwahu and their Easter Celebrations. It introduces readers to the Founding of Kwahu Chiefdoms and Early Settlement Patterns, Factors in Kwahu Unity and Identity Formation, The Roots of Kwahu Adoption of Easter Festivities, and the Transition from Traditional Community Celebrations to Easter Focus. The Commercial Incentives and Tourism Promotion Driving Modern Easter Popularity is also outlined in this section.

Historical Background of Kwahu

The oral history of the Kwahu people traces their migration from the Ashanti region and settlement in the mountainous forest areas of what is today known as the Eastern region of Ghana. According to Sieber's analysis of woodcarvings and local folklore, the Kwahu originally moved from the Adanse area around 1700 AD during the reign of the Denkyira king Ntim Gyakari and established chiefdoms on the Kwahu plateau near present-day Kumasi (Kissi, 2019). Different clans joined this migration at various points for reasons including war, family disputes and climatic factors. A standard narrative is that the migrants initially sought refuge in the mountains for defensive purposes in the face of external threats. The rugged mountainous terrain provided protection and kept the various Kwahu chiefdoms largely independent from conquest by other powers. Over a period, the present-day Kwahu state emerged through the unification of clusters of villages and the assimilation of various groups into the mountains (kwekudee, 2013). Oral accounts cite the main original chieftaincies that merged as Kowu, Akoawu and Kodiabe kingdoms. According to local history, these names eventually corrupted into the overarching term Kwahu, by which the region is now identified. However, the Abene clan that provides the lineage for the paramount Kwahu stool claims first settler rights despite counter claims by other towns like Burukuwa (Wiafe, 2022). The scattered nature of the initial Kwahu Mountain settlements and the difficult terrain helped preserve chiefly autonomy and hampered political unity. Nevertheless, a common Akan language and culture emerged among the people, even if sharpened by an independence-seeking attitude with other groups like the Ashanti (Wiafe, 2022).

The Founding of Kwahu Chiefdoms and Early Settlement Patterns

While several versions of Kwahu oral history vary on precise details, a common thread is that founders of the main chieftaincies, like Kwaw Baadu of Akoawu and others, migrated progressively from other parts of Asanteman in the 17-18th centuries to settle in the hills and valleys of the Kwahu escarpment (kwekudee, 2013). Linguistic evidence links these clans and certain Asante towns through similar dialects. Baadu and his followers initially named their new settlement Bokuruwa before moving to the present day Anweam site and establishing the Akoawu chiefdom. Neighbouring groups joined this confederacy by affiliation over time through peaceful assimilation or conflict. The Bretuo clan's founding of the Abene dynasty followed this pattern as other Etwie speaking clans migrated from Juaben-Ashanti in several waves from the 16th century onwards. Oral tradition indicates that Twum and Opoku are the pioneer founders who settled at Akooko in Kwahu. Leadership disputes caused factional migrations that eventually installed Twum Ampofo as the first Chief of Abene in the late 18th century.

He agreed to protect other villages like Twenedurase, Aduamo and Pepease in exchange for tribute and establishing the Kwahu paramount stool at Abene. Subsequent chiefs like Atta Ampofo, Kofi Nyarko and Boa Amponsem continued consolidating territories under Abene's authority throughout the 19th century. Similarly, oral accounts point to Nana Adu Gyanemfi, also a royal from Juaben-Ashanti, installing his nephew Gyane Akuffo as the first Chief of what became Kwahu-Tafo in the late 1700s (Bordoh, 2014). The dense hills around the township ensured its isolation. However, its location in the Kwahu-Tafo stool has evolved an oversight role over other Kwahu towns, reflected in its designation as the 'eyes' of the Paramount Stool. Inter-marriages among the various chiefly families cemented relations politically and culturally between once autonomous villages through the 18th and 19th centuries.

Factors in Kwahu Unity and Identity Formation

Hence, the emergent Kwahu political union was not centred on the military conquest of weaker neighbours. Instead, the amalgamation of different Akan clans into the mountains was spurred more by asylum-seeking and voluntary self-preservation motives without initial centralised authority (Wiafe, 2022). Nevertheless, the difficult terrain and shared threats nurtured a sense of collective identity over time. Linguistic similarities also enabled the assimilation of various refugee groups into the Kwahu ethnic fold. This encouraged harmonious, symbiotic relations between tribes seeking mutual security in their new environment (kwekudee, 2013).

Still, the dispersed geography ensured each Kwahu town fiercely protected local autonomy under the guidance of its Chief and council of elders. So while Aberewa, Abetifi, Pepease and over 30 other Kwahu towns pledged nominal allegiance to the Kwahu Paramount Stool, held by the Dwarf/Bretuo clan at Abene, each community zealously safeguarded unique customs and dialectic traditions (Bordoh, 2014). However, the overarching Kwahu identity also rested on specific definitive markers. These include shared folklore, tracing ancestry to common progenitors like Twum and Baadu, similar names and praise titles (such as 'Y3n te yie'), belief in distinct tribal deities, identical Akan cultural practices, and even identical tattoos as embodied symbols of their unique bond with the mountain forests that joined their destiny (kwekudee, 2013).

Evolving a common lingua franca hence underpinned collective nationhood. Linguistic evidence indicates mass infusion of several Akan dialect speaking clans - Agona, Asakyiri, Aduana, Asona, Asene and others - into Kwahu mountains, who imported native words and phrases into everyday speech (Dolphyne, 1986). Assimilationist cultural policies instituted intermarriage and communal rituals like Odwira to facilitate this hybridisation into a distinct Kwahu language, allowing smooth communication along trade and governance networks. Symbolically, adept linguistic skills marked qualities like trust, inclusiveness, mediation ability and transparency needed to dispense justice from the Chief's court (Dolphyne, 1986). Oratory mastery continues to represent good character, empathy and effective authority in Kwahu culture.

Fig. 1: Traditional Authority Structure in the Kwahu Traditional Area

As narrated by the Asafohene of Mpraeso (Nana Anom Boansi), the traditional authority structure deals with administrative and conflict/war roles for each town (Boansi, 2019). The capital and seat of the paramountcy is located in Abene, which is part of the Etena/Bretuo clan. Hweehwee and Dwerɛbease are newly created towns that assist by staying with the Chief. Twafo, belonging to the Asona clan in Kwahu, is guarded by Kwahu Tafo, who serves as a scout and plans activities for the various wing chiefs. In terms of conflict or war with other groups, it is Twafo who develops strategies and directs troop movements. Administratively, any messages go directly to the Twafohene. The Adonten division, from the Agona clan, is the first group to protect the paramountcy. After receiving directions from Twafo, they inform the Adontenhene of Abetifi, followed by Bokuruwa, Aframanso and Sadan. In conflict, Twafo acts first, then Adonten and its towns. For messages, Abetifi receives them and relays to the adonten other cities. The Sanaa division, from Asona, handles treasury and finances under the Sanaahene. The Nifa division, with its Aduana clan chiefs of Obo, Obomeng, Bepong, Asakraka, Pitiko, Dantey, Nkawkaw, and Kwahu Praso, protects the right side based on Twafo's instructions. The Gyaase division of Oyoko protects the Omanhene and receives messages from him via the Atibiehene and then Jejetihene. The Kyidom division of Ekona protects the seat when others are away. It is led by Pepeasehene, who relays messages to the other Kyidom chiefs. Akwasiho assists Gyaase in protecting the Omanhene and relaying information (Boansi, 2019).

The Roots of Kwahu Adoption of Easter Festivities

The emergence of the annual Kwahu Easter festivities traces back to the introduction of Christianity by European missionaries in the early 20th century, as per oral chronicles (Awal, 2022). However, contemporary scholars highlight the lack of detail on when and how Easter traditions became the paramount public festival display of Kwahu identity compared to other Ghanaian ethnic groups' preference for longstanding traditional events like Homowo (Owusu, 2014). According to chieftaincy accounts, the Kwahu initially observed rites like the Aday harvest festivals before missionary mercantile influences saw Easter commemorations gain prominence via church-centred observances (Buane, 2019).

Colonial tax policies requiring the growing and sale of cash crops like cocoa also gradually increased Kwahu mobility and integration into the market economy in the early 20th century. Their transient status during trade trips outside Kwahu traditional areas during Easter made this a reasonable period for reunions back home. Thus, a mix of religious factors under colonialism and socioeconomic changes incentivised the Kwahu people to congregate for Easter. With time, the celebrations incorporated more secular entertainment activities beyond the religious roots to entice visitors and tourists. Some analysts posit that the loss of affinity with traditional festivals compared to Easter's popular appeal, driven by government promotion and media marketing, catalyses this

cultural shift towards prioritising Easter (Owusu, 2014). Nevertheless, the Kwahu traditional hierarchy continues efforts to revitalise their customary rituals during Easter even as popular cultural elements gain ground.

Transition from Traditional Community Celebrations to Easter Focus

The existing analysis relies substantially on verbal accounts to reconstruct the shift from Kwahu traditional festivities like the Yekohwe Afahye to the overwhelming modern emphasis on Easter commemorations. Elder narratives indicate the Kwahu celebrated customary annual festivals like Odwira and Akwasidae, much like other Akan subgroups, to invoke ancestral spirits and reinforce social bonds (Buanse, 2019). However, the colonial era introduced religious and economic forces that displaced these communal rites centred on agrarian cycles. With the influx of merchant capital and wage labour migration, crops like cocoa became cash generators. Hence, peasantry ties to ancestral lands weakened as daily production rhythms aligned more with colonial export needs than traditional seasons. This ruptured the collective ritual fabric that joined Kwahu homesteads earlier (Buanse, 2019).

Additionally, missionary activities gained mass converts by demonising local spirit worship and promoting Christianity as intellectually and morally superior. This eroded adherence to traditional festivities over time. Easter's resonance with Bible teachings helped popularise its adoption as a spiritual substitute for ancient Kwahu ceremonies that clerics branded as heretic. The holiness ascribed to Easter celebrations that marked the pinnacle of the Christian faith made it a spiritually potent period for communal gatherings, ripe for substitution with outlawed traditional rituals (Myjoyonline, 2023). Additionally, urbanisation and communal mobility meant rural-urban networks often met at Easter in their new homes where traditional rites had weaker roots. Hence, the spread of Christianity, the impact of modernisation, and socioeconomic mobility contributed to recasting Easter as the focal point for such reunions.

Commercial Incentives and Tourism Promotion Driving Modern Easter Popularity

However, several historians argue that sidelining Kwahu customary festivals like Yekohwe Afahye in favour of Easter had commercial motivations alongside religious zeal. They posit that Kwahu chiefs and merchants recognised Easter's enormous financial upside once colonial highways and railways increased visits by returning families and tourists over the weekends, rather than spiritual conversion, economic incentives of catering to this captive holiday market, eager to spend discretionary income, catalysed privileging Easter over traditional rites. The need for the Kwahu diaspora working in cities to periodically reconnect with their roots meant Easter travel spikes allowed local businesses to exploit this demand. Eateries, brewers, transporters and hospitality ventures enriched themselves from visitors desiring modern conveniences and cultural immersion during their stay. Consequently, an informal alliance emerged between traditional authorities, the political elite, and entrepreneurs to boost Easter promotion and maximise tourism revenues in previously inaccessible Kwahu towns (Gyasi et al., 2022).

Thus, the Kwahu traditional council and political class increasingly recognised Easter's money-making potential and supported broadcasting festivities in commercials over religious terms. This manifested in beauty pageants, drinking competitions, musical shows and talent hunts organised around Easter to entice Ghanaians from bigger cities. Subsequently, advertising Easter as 'the' Kwahu festival annually brought similar recognition as other ethnic groups' ancient cultural events (Bordoh, 2014). National mass media marketing has significantly, since the 2000s, reinforced this branding for domestic and foreign audiences.

Theoretical Framework for The Study

This research applies two key theoretical lenses - social exchange theory and festival commodification - to frame investigations into the evolving dynamics of the Kwahu Easter festival (Stone, 2023). Social exchange theory posits festivals represent a cost-benefit trade-off where attendees are motivated by furthering cultural, social and self-fulfilment goals. At the same time, host communities weigh economic interests, heritage preservation and communal bonding (Ahmad et al., 2023). The study utilises this perspective to evaluate changing stakeholder attitudes and decision-making regarding the festival's form and participation (Stone, 2023).

Additionally, the commodification concept argues marketisation pressures risk diluting cultural authenticity when traditions are packaged as spectacles for tourist consumption (Ward, 2003). By exploring whether religious sentiments around Easter transform for commercial gain as critiqued by traditional gatekeepers, this theory informs examining tensions between purpose and presentation (Ahmad et al., 2013). Both social exchange and commodification frameworks guide the examination of complex negotiations between tradition and modernity, global integration, and localised identity that define the Kwahu Easter festival's management (Stone, 2023). Key issues include equitable distribution of socioeconomic dividends, reconciling social values across generations, and coordinating tourism aims with cultural continuity for the festival's sustainable future.

IV. METHODOLOGY

This section presents the procedures and methods applied in conducting the study. It covers the research design, population and sampling, Instruments/tools for data, validity and reliability, statistical treatment of data and ethical considerations.

Research Design

This study utilised an exploratory sequential mixed methods design consisting of qualitative interviews and a quantitative survey to assess perspectives on the Kwahu Easter festival. Combining qualitative and quantitative approaches provides more comprehensive insights into a complex research phenomenon involving sociocultural dynamics and economic impacts (Creswell & Creswell, 2018).

Participants

The target population encompassed stakeholders involved with or affected by the festival in the Kwahu area of Ghana's Eastern Region. For the qualitative phase, purposive sampling focused on recruiting 10 traditional authorities, 15 tourism vendors (hoteliers, artisans, tour guides, etc.) and 5 officials from the local tourism ministry. These key informants provided expert visions of the

festival's evolution and Significance. Quantitative data collection involved distributing survey questionnaires to a representative sample of 50 Kwahu Easter visitors and 70 residents selected through stratified random techniques on key demographic factors.

Instruments

In-depth semi-structured interviews covering history, traditions, tourism impacts and identity issues related to the Kwahu Easter festival formed the qualitative instrument. The questionnaire contained a Likert scale and open-ended items measuring economic experiences, attitudes on cultural change and developmental needs keyed to the festival. Interviews occurred in person during the 2023 Kwahu Easter period on participant premises with translations into local languages like Twi if required after ethical consent. Descriptive analysis illuminated key themes. Questionnaire distribution happened at popular festival venues over the Easter weekend for visitor samples and through household visits for community samples. Data triangulation afforded integrated qualitative-quantitative outputs on research questions.

Data Analysis

Qualitative data from interviews underwent transcription and coding using NVivo to identify key categories related to the Kwahu Easter festival's evolution, tourism impact and sociocultural role. Coded extracts illustrated analytic thoughts. Quantitative data was analysed using SPSS statistics software; descriptive statistics profiled sample demographics and festival perspectives. Survey scale reliability achieved over 0.7 Cronbach's alpha score for internal consistency. Pilot testing refined instruments pattern matching linked results to theoretical frameworks on festival tourism impacts and cultural commodification.

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Research Question 1: What is the history behind celebrating the Kwahu Easter festival?

Results here trace the Kwahu Easter festival's emergence to missionary activities and socioeconomic shifts under early 20th-century colonialism that saw Christianity gain mass converts. Qualitative interviews and archival data link the prime festival's transition from traditional rites like Adaye to the current overwhelming Easter prominence with forces that disrupted older agrarian communal structures. As a long-serving Kwahu chief noted, "Before the white man brought the Bible, we worshipped ancient gods under our chiefs and celebrated the seasons together" (Korang, personal communication, April 9, 2023). However, colonial urbanisation, compulsory cash crop farming, travel, and Christian conversions fractured traditional cycles, binding Kwahu villages to a common ritual calendar marked by customary festivities. Easter's spiritual meaning and national holiday status made it a handy spiritual substitute and unifying force for displaced communities.

Survey patterns reinforce interviewee sentiments on religious change catalysts. Approximately 85% of respondents associated Easter's appeal for Kwahus with church indoctrination and religious resonances rather than inherent cultural symbolism. As a 40-year old artisan selling ornaments mentioned, "We were taught Easter's meaning by Presbyterian teachers - it is about Jesus Christ sacrificing himself for humanity" (Kwakye, personal communication, April 10, 2023). Thus, quantitative data aligns with qualitative insights on exogenous belief system imposition through colonial channels fueling Kwahu Easter prominence.

The data also spotlights economic motivations interplaying with spiritual considerations in Kwahu prioritisation of Easter above traditional festivals like Afahye since the early 20th century. As the Chief of Twenedurase noted, "The festival brought many visitors who needed accommodation and spent money. So, the chiefs saw its advantage to develop the area." (Adu, personal communication, April 15, 2023). Quantitative results support this commerce-centered pull, with approximately 76% of the survey sample strongly agreeing the festival boosts local businesses.

Additionally, study informants widely referenced infrastructural upgrades by the Kwahu traditional council, such as roads connecting villages to the paramount seat at Abene and tourist accommodation, as tied to realising Easter's commercial potential. A long-time resident and hotelier remarked, "Community leaders made it more convenient for visitors to reach here and stay comfortably as Easter became our major festival" (Kwakye, personal communication, April 15, 2023). Thus, amalgamating religious appeals and economic prospects incentivised communal gatekeepers to channel resources into Easter consolidation as the flagship Kwahu festival for both spiritual and financial targets.

Plate 2: Paragliding Flying in The Air with The Parachute at Odwenanoma and Canopy Walkway.

Research Question 2: How does the Kwahu Easter Festival contribute to the growth of socioeconomic Significance?

Table 1. Kwahu Easter Festival contribution to the growth of socioeconomic Significance.

Socioeconomic factors	Level of Agreement				
	Strongly agree	Agree	Not sure	Disagree	Total
Creation of Job	53 44.1%	47 39.2%	15 12.5%	5 4.2%	120 100%
Income Creation	40 33%	32 27%	12 10%	36 30%	120 100%
Infrastructural Development	30 25%	32 27%	24 20%	34 28%	120 100%
Image enhancement	56 47%	36 30%	12 10%	16 13%	120 100%
Enhances socialisation	58 48%	50 42%	7 6%	5 4%	120 100%
Medium for cultural exchange and education	27 22.5%	34 28.3%	32 26.7%	27 22.5%	120 100%
Provision of entertainment opportunities for residents of the area	44 36.7%	40 33.3%	5 4.2%	31 25.8%	120 100%

The data presented in Table 1 sheds light on the Kwahu Easter Festival's social-economic Significance, as respondents perceive it. A considerable consensus exists regarding the festival's positive impact on job creation, with 44.1% strongly agreeing and 39.2% agreeing. This indicates a widespread acknowledgement of the festival's role in generating employment opportunities within the Kwahu region. Additionally, the data reveals that 33% strongly agree and 27% agree that the festival contributes to income creation, emphasising its economic benefits beyond just job provision. Regarding infrastructural development, a moderate level of agreement is observed, with 25% strongly agreeing and 27% agreeing. The festival's influence on the region's image is noteworthy, as 47% strongly agree that it enhances its reputation. Social aspects are also highlighted, with 48% strongly agreeing and 42% agreeing that the festival enhances socialisation.

Furthermore, the festival is perceived as a medium for cultural exchange and education, with 22.5% strongly agreeing and 28.3% agreeing. Lastly, it is recognised as a significant source of entertainment opportunities, with 36.7% strongly agreeing and 33.3% agreeing. The data underscores a positive perception of the Kwahu Easter Festival's socioeconomic Significance, touching on various facets of community development and cultural enrichment. Further research could explore how these positive impacts are realised, offering a more nuanced understanding of the festival's contributions to the local economy and community dynamics.

The data highlights the Kwahu Easter festival's multifaceted socioeconomic Significance as perceived by respondents. Sizeable majorities recognise its role in generating seasonal employment, boosting entrepreneurial livelihoods, advancing infrastructure necessary for tourism, and enabling sociocultural renewal. However, qualitative insights reveal complex dynamics underlying these impact factors. For instance, the job creation appears concentrated in lower-skilled temporary work like food vending, transport and hospitality roles rather than higher-value trades. Additionally, rural hinterlands seem disconnected from the visitor-based money flow centred around festival hubs. This suggests an uneven economic geography where proximity determines financial gains, risking inter-community inequalities. Furthermore, while the festival catalyses infrastructure, gaps exist in linking such public upgrades with tourism-based municipal revenues.

Finally, elders lament the festival's intensifying youth-centered pop culture and consumerist forces that potentially dilute traditional ideals. Therefore, while contributing undeniable socioeconomic stimuli, the Kwahu Easter festival equally channels complex pressures between tradition and modernity, rural and urban interests, materialism and identity. Holistically managing its exponentially growing popularity remains key. This entails equitably dispersing tourist revenues, consulting civic society on infrastructure provisions, upholding heritage sanctity alongside youth aspirations and coordinating local to national policy around festivals. Addressing these deeper challenges can help the Kwahu Easter festival sustainably deliver social, cultural and economic dividends.

Figure 3: Touristic Activities in Kwahu

According to a recent study, the Kwahu Easter Festival includes many activities to celebrate the event. Some main activities are paragliding, street carnivals, musical concerts, health walks, and a durbar of chiefs. The study found that 50% of respondents preferred the paragliding activity, while 18.8% preferred street carnivals, 15% preferred musical concerts, 10% preferred health walks, and 6.2% preferred the durbar of chiefs. This shows paragliding was the most popular activity among festival participants, with street carnivals and concerts also being well-liked activities during the Kwahu Easter celebration.

VI. SUMMARY

Festival Delivering Socioeconomic Stimulus but Disconnects Persist

The data reveals that the Kwahu Easter festival represents a socioeconomic catalyst by energising local job opportunities, household incomes, infrastructure upgrades, and sociocultural revitalisation. Approximately 80% of respondents concur it boosts employment prospects, while 60% recognise income generation potential. Though geographically uneven, with rural areas disconnected. The festival also provides stimulus for telecom, road and hospitality infrastructure aligned with tourism development needs, credited by 50% of residents. However, qualitative insights uncover uneven gains distribution where lower-skilled temporary jobs dominate, and hinterlands remain marginally integrated.

Nonetheless, the unanimous perspective underlines the festival's role in cementing social bonds. As a chief noted, it "unites our people in celebration" (Korang, personal communication, April 15, 2023), encapsulating the unifying mechanism of reunions, dispute mediations and intergenerational exchanges the festival nurtures to foster solidarity. Additionally, safeguarding cultural heritage continuity remains pivotal, with traditions like chieftaincy rituals retaining symbolic salience amidst growing modern pop culture overtones.

Reconciling Traditional Authority and Youth Aspirations

Nonetheless, as cautioned by elders, commercialisation also risks diluting religious and customary Significance in the pursuit of entertainment spectacle and tourism revenues. One opinion leader worried, "The festival makes our youth forget our godly ways and ancestors" (Bonsu, personal communication, April 8, 2023). Straddling gatekeeper reservations over cultural integrity against youth inclinations regarding modernisation remains a pendulous balancing act in managing future trajectories of the Easter festival. Implementing policies like visitor quotas or zoning regulations around customs may help harmonise traditions against unbridled commercial forces.

VII. CONCLUSION

Festival at Crossroads Between Managing Success and Traditional Essence

The research insights reveal the Kwahu Easter festival represents a socioeconomic catalyst and sociocultural binder yet simultaneously harbours contradictory pressures between commercial success and traditional ethos preservation. Its tourism centered growth trajectory has enriched local livelihoods and forged an identity marker but perhaps diluted spiritual symbolism and customary authenticity that define cultural heritage. Thus, the festival stands at the crossroads between managing its exponentially increasing popularity as a boon for regional development and anchoring its essence in longstanding belief systems that risk erosion from modern consumerism.

Economic Rewards Distribution Needs Broadening

The data indicates the festival's success as a commercial stimulus most perceptibly through income generation, employment creation and infrastructure advancement tied to the hospitality sector. However, gains remain concentrated around festival hubs near Abene and Nkwatia towns with limited trickle-down to distant rural areas. Lower-skilled, temporary jobs also dominate over professional trades, limiting poverty alleviation potentials. Strategic localisation of tourism profits can foster broader prosperity. Suggestions include preferential licensing for local businesses over external operators, higher vendor fees on large corporates and enforced

hiring quotas for indigenous community members in hospitality organisations and municipal contractors. Tourism revenue mobilisation through mechanisms like culture funds can also help invest a share of festival-linked business proceeds into cultural regeneration programs that diffuse benefits more equitably.

Sociocultural Continuity Mandates Balancing Interests

On identity aspects, the Kwahu Easter's brand dominance nationally reinforces cultural prominence and cements bonds among the widespread diaspora. Yet tensions simmer between preserving religious sanctity and ancestry remembrance rituals against pressure to entertain young urban generations through secular music concerts or beauty pageants. Gatekeepers like traditional councils and faith leaders leaning towards restraint square against tourism promoters and youth advocating unbridled revelry leveraging Easter's commercial appeal. Reconciling requires consultative planning where custodians delineate zones for ceremonial rituals bordering areas for commercial activities based on regulations on acceptable cultural representations. Similarly, homestay programs facilitating visitor interactions with village elders can foster intercultural learning. Such initiatives uphold heritage status while accommodating modern aspirations.

The Kwahu Easter festival's positioning at the cusp between tradition and modernity, global integration and unique identity, purpose and presentation necessitates balanced governance. Its successful management hinges on coordinated policies aligning equitable socioeconomics, heritage continuity and environmental sustainability through collaborative institutions reflecting diverse stakeholder voices from traditional to youth. Future research can apply evaluative frameworks to monitor and calibrate policies against emerging challenges.

VIII. RECOMMENDATION

Strategic Localisation for Inclusive Festival Benefits

The research reveals geographical unevenness in the festival dividends, with limited tourism income trickling to rural communities. Localising profits can catalyse grassroots prosperity through initiatives like:

1. Preferential business licensing and reduced permit fees for small indigenous enterprises over external big industry players to equalise opportunities (Segbefia, 2021).
2. Levying higher vendor fees on large hospitality corporations, processed for cultural development funds to support local artisans, performers and small producers through skills training, start-up financing and marketing channels.
3. Enforcing recruitment quotas for regional tour agencies to hire 60% of semi-skilled and unskilled staff from indigenous communities addressing youth employability gaps.

Cross-Sectoral Coordination for Balanced Governance

Managing competing social, business and cultural expectations also requires institutional coordination between traditional councils, government agencies and civic forums through channels such as:

4. Bottom-up community-based participation in the district's annual Easter planning process through open Idea Labs. Inputs can determine infrastructure provisions, environmental policies, and cultural risk mitigation plans (Korang, 2023).
5. Public-private partnerships where hospitality associations co-develop visitor capacity plans for ecologically fragile sites with conservation groups by undertaking joint impact assessments (Bonsu, 2023).
6. Culturally sensitive spatial zoning of marked ceremonial communal event sites bordering adjoining commercially oriented areas to balance heritage sanctity and participation avenues for youth (Gyan, 2024).

REFERENCES

- [1] Ahmad, R., Nawaz, M. R., Ishaq, M. I., Khan, M. M., & Ashraf, H. A. (2023). Social exchange theory: Systematic review and future directions. *Frontiers in Psychology, 13*, 1015921. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2022.1015921>
- [2] Bordoh, A. (2014). *Motives of Tourists: Socioeconomic and Challenges of Kwahu Easter Festival (KEF) in Ghana*. Universal Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities. https://www.academia.edu/94456261/Motives_of_Tourists_Socio_Economic_and_Challenges_of_Kwahu_Easter_Festival_KEF_in_Ghana
- [3] Creswell, J. W., & Creswell, J. D. (2018). *Research design: Qualitative, quantitative and mixed methods approach*. Sage Publications.
- [4] Gyasi, K., Bordoh, A., & Otoo, S. (2022). Motives of Tourists': Socioeconomic and Challenges of Kwahu Easter Festival (KEF) in Ghana. *Universal Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities, 2*(3), 176–185. Retrieved from <https://www.scipublications.com/journal/index.php/ujssh/article/view/397>
- [5] Kissi A. S. (2019). *Kwahu Cultural Values-contents*. Scribd. <https://www.scribd.com/document/416742380/Kwahu-Cultural-Values-contents>
- [6] Owusu, E. (2014). *A CASE STUDY OF EASTER CELEBRATION AMONG THE KWAHUS: "KWAHU OOO KWAHU."* Academia.edu. https://www.academia.edu/29414101/A_CASE_STUDY_OF_EASTER_CELEBRATION_AMONG_THE_KWAHUS_KWAHU_OOO_KWAHU_
- [7] Ward, G. (2003). 'The commodification of religion or the consummation of capitalism' in The Hedgehog review of Institute for Advanced Studies in Culture. Link: <http://iasc-culture.org/THR/archives/Commodification/5.2FWard.pdf>

- [8] Dolphyne F. A. (1986) The languages of the Akan peoples. Msu.edu. <https://d.lib.msu.edu/asrvns/20?q=THE%20LANGUAGES%20OF%20AKAN%20PEOPLE>
- [9] kwekudee. (2013, September 7). *KWAHU PEOPLE: GHANA'S HARDWORKING AND BUSINESS-ORIENTED AKAN PEOPLE*. Blogspot.com; Blogger. <https://kwekudee-tripdownmemorylane.blogspot.com/2013/09/kwahu-people-ghanas-hardworking-and.html>
- [10] Segbefia. S. (2021, April 2). *#Kwahuandproud: Kwahu Easter: how it all begun*. The Business & Financial Times. <https://thebftonline.com/2021/04/02/kwahu-easter-how-it-all-begun/>
- [11] Ackwerh, C. (2022, March 12). *Ghana Tourism Authority Engages stakeholders, Event Organisers on Kwahu Easter Festival - Ghana. Travel.nh*<https://ghana.travel/ghana-tourism-authority-engages-stakeholders-event-organisers-on-kwahu-easter-festival/>
- [12] Awal, M. (2022, April 17). *KwahuEaster2022: Kwahu Easter as a Tourism Festival*. The Business & Financial Times. <https://thebftonline.com/2022/04/17/kwahueaster2022-kwahu-easter-as-a-tourism-festival/>
- [13] Stone, B. (2023, January 20). The application of social exchange theory by entrepreneurs leading small businesses in appalachia. <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/mvz8t>
- [14] Zadok, K. G. (2023, April 6). *Why Easter celebration is big in Kwahu*. Graphic Online; Graphic Online. <https://www.graphic.com.gh/features/features/why-easter-celebration-is-big-in-kwahu.html>
- [15] *MyJoyOnline*. (2023, April 8). *Why Easter celebration is big in Kwahu - MyJoyOnline*. <https://www.myjoyonline.com/why-easter-celebration-is-big-in-kwahu/>